

**THE HISTORY OF LITERARY NIGHTS OF SUBHONQULIKHAN,
RULER OF BUKHARA KHANTY, SCIENTIST AND POET****Sherxon Qorayev,**

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docent, ph.f.d. E-mail: sherxonqorayev18@gmail.com**Abstract**

This article talks about the creativity, poetry and writings of the representative of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty, the ruler of the Bukhara Khanate, Subhonqulikhan.

Poetry evenings with the participation of poets in the presence of the ruler and its influence on the development of our classic literature are analyzed.

Key words: *Alias, tatabbu', science of medicine, science of astrology, masnavi.*

Introduction. In the history of world literature, the researches conducted on the research of literary processes, literary environments, heritage of representatives of court literature serve to ensure the development of its theory on the basis of the history of science.

Analysis of literature on the topic. One of the important sources of the Middle Ages, Muhammad Yusuf Munshi's "History of Muqimkhani" tells about the history of the Ashtarkhanid ruler Subhanqulikhan. Although Mir Muhammad Amin Bukhari's historical treatise "Ubaidullanama" seems like a continuation of "History of Muqimkhani", it is one of the treatises that talks about the reign of Subhanquli Khan and Ubaidullah Khan. The period of Subhanquli Khan is also covered in detail in Muhit al-Tawarikh by Muhammad Amin Bukhari, who served

in the Ashtarkhanid dynasty. The work "Dastur ul-muluk" by Khwaja Samandar Termizi on our topic is considered one of the important historical sources of Subhonquli Khan period [14, 81]".

Research methodology. At the time when the foundations of the Third Renaissance period are being laid in today's New Uzbekistan, the formation of new principles of the criteria of our national literature and history based on the advanced methodological methods that have emerged in world literature, and the research of palace literature and literary gatherings in the history of Uzbek literature are of urgent importance. A number of methods and methods, such as historical consistency, historical-comparative, contextual and complex analysis, chronological classification and description, were used to cover the topic of the article.

Analysis and results . The full name of Bukhara Khan, poet and scientist Subhanqulikhan is Saidmuhammad Subhanqulikhan ibn Saidnadr Muhammadkhan [1, 92]. As Khoja Samandar Termizi wrote, Subhonqulikhan (1625-1702) "*owner of cabbage, heir of Jamshid estate, Farrukh Shavkatli*" wrote poems. Subhonquli Khan wrote poems in his literary gatherings and in connection with various events. According to Muhammad Amin Bukhari, when Subhonquli Khan heard the news of Khiva Khan Anusha Urganji's dethronement and a needle in his eye, he "*opened his lips in a smile of joy and read this verse: (Content:)*

Agar mulkka (biror kishi) rahna solsa,

Boshini olib tashlagan yaxshi.

Lashkar ishonchsiz bo'lsa tarqatib yuborgan yaxshi. [4, 92-93] "

In Muhammad Yusuf Munshi's "History of Muqimkhani" the following poem of Subhanqulikhan is mentioned:

Qaddam zi g'ami hajri tu chun sham' shud, ammo

Tore zi visoli tu ba changam narasida.

Dar dida fitad kosh, Nishony, guli ro'yash,

Aftodani gul garchi ziyon ast ba dida [5, 117] .

(Content: *Because of the sadness of your departure, my step has become like a candle, but because of you, there is no net in the forest of nets. Betrothed, see the flower on your face, The falling of flowers is a loss.*)

Ashtarkhani ruler Subhonqulikhan himself recited his poems and invited other poets to the mushairas held in Nishani Palace [<https://ziyouz.uz/ilm-va-fan/tarikh/ozbekiston-hukmdorlari/subhonqulikhan/>] ". Khan was always surrounded by many poets [9, 38]. There were two currents in the cultural life of this period, especially in literature. One was the palace literature, at the top of which stood Subhonqulikhan himself. Muhammad Bade' ibn Muhammad Sharif, a Samarkand poet known by the nickname "Maleho", writes that there were about 150 poets in the palace at that time [9, 85]. Because Subhonquli Khan had a great passion for literature and liked to gather poets and scientists around him and hold literary gatherings and scientific discussions.

During the Ashtarkhanids period, literature and poetry in the Persian and Uzbek (mostly Khiva) languages developed in the Bukhara khanate [10, 38]. Haji Abdulazim Shariy, the author of "Ain al-Tawarikh" ("Fountain of Histories"), praised the literary work of Subhonqulikhan and wrote: "*He also had a high taste for poetry.*" *They nicknamed Nishany. Poet Kamal said tatabbu' to the verse* [4, 9] ".

After Turdi Faroghi Subhankuli Khan, who served in the palace of Abdulaziz Khan, took the throne, he sharply criticized the ruler's policy and left the palace. Literary scholar Umid Bekmuhammad writes, "*He was also a poet like Subhonquli Khan, wrote poetry under the pseudonym Turdi Faroghi, and his writings were of social significance rather than the domestic and love topics that were customary at that time.*

Although Subhonqulikhan was a poet and a doctor, he raised the scientific and cultural center in Bukhara and tried to help artists, especially Turdi, Turdibek

wanted to put an end to conflicts between the clans and feuds more than to appreciate his personality and creativity. Realizing that he could not stay longer in the palace, Turdi finished the poem saying, "There is not a single person left at the door of the Khan, only one owner of science, only a few notes of sukum are used, the work of your hands does not come, everyone is a liar and a liar", and he goes to his clan [<https://kh-davron.uz/kutubkhona/uzbek/umid-bekmuhammad-saroyga-sigmagan-sohir.html>] ”.

Turdi Farogiy finished the work "Comic about Subhonquli Khan" in 1691. Until then, the poet, who wandered the country for six years, saw the condition of the people with his own eyes. Turdi Faroghi was one of the few poets who criticized the ruler of the time he lived in and fought for enlightenment [<https://shosh.uz/ibrat-ila-boq-kuzing-tufroqqa-tolmasdan-burun/>]".

According to Muhammad Amin Bukhari, the court poets, "poets of sweet words, rare words in front of ul Hazrat [4, 52] " , dedicated to him, recited verses and odes. Continent (Content):

***Oy sening ostonangdan ketguncha, ey janob kayvon,
Zarrin oftob o'z tanini supurgi qilib ketadi.
Kayvon manzillik podshoh, Iskandar Rumiyan o'zing,
Sening g'ayrat dengizingdan yettinchi osmon bir ko'prikdir,
Xuddi porlab turgan quyosh qarshisida xira yulduzdek,
Jamshidga nisbat qilsam oliy podshohni ko'raman.
Shoh Abu-l-G'oziy jahon shohi Subhonquli,
Dinu dunyoning ulug' nodir podshohi.***

At the poetry evenings of Subhanquli Khan, the court poet Maulana Nainiy Balkhi recited the following ode: (Translation)

***Hazrat Subhonqulixon davlati bilan,
Turon shohidan taxtni tortib oldi.
Shohning nomi bilan falak sikka urdi,***

Xatiblar birakay xutba o'qidilar. [4, 53].

Subhonqulikhan Nishani liked to organize literary gatherings under him.

Subhonqulikhan wrote a number of scientific books on medicine. Therefore, literary critic Rustam Jabbarov said about this work: *"Another work of Subhonkulikhan dedicated to medicine - the only copy of the treatise "Khulosatul-hukamo" is kept in the library of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences."* In addition to "Tibbi Subhani" about medicine, Subhonquli Khan also wrote a book in Persian language "Ihyo ut tibbi Subhani" ("Subhonquli's book that revives medicine"). A manuscript copy of this work (Inv. #2101, 301 sheets) is kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies[4, 10]. Subhonqulikhan also wrote a work on foil called "Ramali Subhaniy" (UzFA ShI, inv #4260). According to his decree, a collection of fatwas named "Fatavoi Subhani" was also developed[18, 93]. The treatise "Lub-lavoih al-qamar fi-l-ikhtiyarat" ("Essence of the moon's light for astrology") on the science of astrology (astronomy) was also written by the khan [9, 75]. It consists of several films, two articles and a conclusion. In 1855, Khan of Khiva gave it to Muhammad Yaqub, the minister of Sayyid Muhammad Khan, and Muhammad Yusuf Raji translated it into Uzbek and published it himself. (See: OR FA ShI – 1, №1205) [17, 185]. Khan Jalaluddin wrote a commentary on Rumi's masnavis in Persian entitled "Risola dar manaviyi bayti "Masnavii"". This commentary is kept in the manuscript treasury of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni [9, 87].

Conclusions and suggestions. In short, Subhonqulikhan's work and literary gatherings served the development of science and classic literature of his time. It can be said that the literary gatherings of the Ashtarkhanid era embodied the traditions of the countries of the Muslim East, especially the Timurids and Shaybanids, and further developed these traditions, and served to improve literature and the literary environment and literary processes. Such gatherings,

which are considered a component of the history of Uzbek classic literature, served as a kind of school for writers of later periods.

Of course, the study and research of the literary environment of Subhonkuli Khan's period will enrich the history of Uzbek literature with new information.

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